

RHYTHM AND ALGORITHM: THE SYNERGY OF MUSIC EDUCATION WITH ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

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Abstract. *This article discusses the utilization of new opportunities in music education through the integration of music and artificial intelligence (AI). It explores how AI can enhance the effectiveness and appeal of lessons, create personalized learning paths, and positively impact students through interactive programs. The article also covers the automation of analysis and evaluation systems, and highlights the significance of AI in acquiring practical skills such as working with sound and composition, as well as theoretical knowledge in music theory and music history. Furthermore, it examines the role of AI in developing musical skills and competencies.*

Keywords: *music education, AI, music software and applications, Yousician, Tonara, SmartMusic, Google Magenta, Amper Music.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada musiqa va sun'iy intellekt integratsiyasi orqali musiqa ta'limida yangicha imkoniyatlardan foydalanish, darslarni yanada samarador va qiziqarli olib borishni SI yordamida takomillashtirish, individual ta'lim yo'llarini yaratish, interfaol dasturlar bilan ishlashning o'quvchilarga ijobiy ta'siri, tahlil va baholash tizimlarini avtomatlashtirish, ovoz va kompozitsiya bilan ishlash kabi amaliy bilimlarni, musiqa nazariyasi va musiqa tarixi kabi nazariy bilimlarni egallashda, ko'nikmalarni shakllantirishda SI ning ahamiyati haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *musiqa ta'limi, SI, musiqiy dastur va ilovalar, Yousician, Tonara, SmartMusic, Google Magenta, Amper Music.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье представлена информация об использовании новых возможностей в музыкальном образовании посредством интеграции музыки и искусственного интеллекта, совершенствовании проведения уроков с помощью ИИ для повышения их эффективности и привлекательности, создании индивидуальных образовательных траекторий, положительном влиянии работы с интерактивными программами на учащихся, автоматизации систем анализа и оценки. Также рассматривается важность ИИ в приобретении практических навыков, таких как работа со звуком и композицией, теоретических знаний в области теории и истории музыки, а также в формировании музыкальных умений.*

Ключевые слова: *музыкальное образование, ИИ, музыкальные программы и приложения, Yousician, Tonara, SmartMusic, Google Magenta, Amper Music.*

Today, “Artificial Intelligence” is rapidly entering every field. This integration in the education system began much earlier, but the participation of artificial intelligence in music education and music literacy classes is gaining momentum today. The rapid penetration of technological changes into the education system is mainly attributed to the fact that representatives of the modern “Gen Z and Gen Alpha”[1] generation were born in the age of technology and were raised in this developed environment. That is, representatives of the

younger generation cannot accept traditional lessons and methods; their scattered attention and very high level of interest in everything has led to the rapid growth of modern education and keeping pace with the times.

The ability of the AI algorithm to learn based on past data is an important feature, for example, computer accompaniment technology, where AI is capable of listening to a human performer and providing accompaniment. Artificial intelligence also controls interactive composition technology, in which the computer creates music in response to live performance. There are other AI applications in music that cover not only musical composition, production, and performance, but also how music is sold and consumed. Several music player programs have also been developed to use voice recognition and natural language processing technology to control music playback.[2]

The disruptive and transformative power of this new technological development requires educational systems to adapt for its use and integration as a didactic and pedagogical resource. From this perspective, a systematic literature review was conducted to analyze the didactic potential of generative AI tools in developing artistic creativity in music education. The research results confirm that the introduction of AI into music education paves the way for a more personalized, interactive, and effective learning experience. Additionally, the analysis identifies nine main directions for the application of AI in music education: virtual and augmented reality (VR; VA); individualization of learning, intelligent tutoring systems; composition assistants; enhanced historical and contextual education; assessment systems; interactive listening skill development and music theory systems; and tools for musical collaboration and performance. [3]

In music education, pedagogical approaches and their connection with creativity are crucial. This is because music lessons involve not only theoretical but primarily practical processes. Modern trends, technologies, particularly AI, play a significant role in making music literacy lessons more effective and engaging.

In Uzbekistan, music lessons are mainly taught in general education schools from the 1st to the 7th grade. Music lessons are held once a week for one hour, and the educational process in primary grades is mainly carried out through five activities. These include: musical literacy, listening to music, group singing, performing rhythmic movements corresponding to the music, and playing children's instruments. When organizing these activities in conjunction with modern technologies, particularly AI, the following opportunities may arise:

1. Creating individualized learning paths (personalization): Today, along with studying the experience of foreign countries, the greatest achievement in education is its personalization. AI can offer specific exercises, tasks, and lesson materials based on students' knowledge level, errors, and interests, such as: solfeggio, rhythm, or note reading exercises tailored to each student. Systems that monitor student development speed and provide feedback.

2. With the help of AI-based applications, students can work with: Virtual orchestras, pianos, or audio experiments. They practice with AI programs that automatically analyze the melody, rhythmic structure, consistency, and dynamics of the music they play (for example, Yousician[5], Tonara[6], SmartMusic[7]). These programs open up wide opportunities for personalized learning. In this case, without the teacher's help, the program shows the student where and what they did wrong.

3. Understanding the psychology of student learning based on neurotechnology and artificial intelligence:

Through AI, students' emotional state, attention span, or stress level can be determined, allowing the teacher or system to adapt the lesson accordingly. This is especially useful for: reducing anxiety during performance and choosing effective methods in high-stress situations.

4. Automation of analysis and evaluation systems

Artificial intelligence can analyze the student's performance (identifying incorrect notes, rhythmic errors), track progress and display it graphically, and automatically conduct post-lesson assessments.

5. Working with sound and composition (creative aspects): With the help of AI, students can: create melodic tunes or rhythmic fragments, compose in collaboration with AI (for example, Google Magenta[8], Amper Music[9]). In addition, there are sufficient possibilities for editing one's own voice in various styles and transcribing music into notation using AI, which is quite popular nowadays.

6. Studying the history and theory of music using AI Through AI chatbots (such as ChatGPT, DeepSeek), students can: learn concepts of music theory through interactive conversation. They can acquire knowledge about Uzbek and world musical literature, composers, musical genres, periods, and styles through question-and-answer sessions.

For several years, a paradigm shift has been observed in educational ecosystems due to the exponential growth of technological resources, which is simultaneously stimulating the renewal of research and pedagogical practices. From this perspective, the gradual introduction of artificial intelligence in the classroom has been a major change in understanding education, particularly music teaching, as it has been noted that artificial intelligence is leading music education into a more efficient and intelligent era, where resources are personalized, discipline adherence is strengthened, and new opportunities are offered for the development of artistic and creative skills.[3]

When conducting lessons using AI, students' ability to complete independent assignments, their creativity, personalization of learning along with having their own special personal curriculum and methodology, providing critical feedback when completing tasks, and pointing out mistakes and shortcomings will improve students' learning skills and enhance the quality of the lesson.

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